

Title: ICOs Disrupting Traditional Funding Models

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INTRODUCTION:

Just through June and July of 2017 more than \$1 billion dollars have been raised through this new fundraising instrument. Startups have raised more money through ICOs than through VC funding.

AIM:

To discuss the longevity of this phenomenon and possible long-term effects for the industry: Angels, VCs, PEs and Hedge Funds.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Based on statistical data available through open sources.

CONCLUSIONS:

Traditional investment companies may need to reposition their offering to stay competitive in the everchanging business environment.

KEYWORDS:

ICO, Crow Sale, Tokens, Blockchain, VC, PE, Angel Investors, Investors, Finance

BIOGRAPHY:

Michael Kapilkov holds an MBA from IE Business School. He is a partner at Datrixo, and serves on the advisory boards of several startups.